

LINGUOCULTURAL STUDY OF TOPONYMS IN ENGLISH FOLKLORE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF *BEOWULF* AND ENGLISH FOLK TALES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20376457>

Abstract. This paper explores the linguocultural significance of toponyms in English folklore, focusing on the epic *Beowulf* and selected English folk tales: *Robin Hood*, *Jack the Giant Killer*, and *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh*. Toponyms in these works are not merely geographical markers but carry deep cultural, symbolic, and historical meanings. Through comparative analysis, the study demonstrates how place names reflect cultural identity, social values, mythological worldview, and the opposition between familiar and чужой (“self vs. other”). The research highlights the role of toponyms in constructing narrative space and preserving collective memory within English oral tradition.

Keywords: toponym, linguoculturology, folklore, Beowulf, English fairy tales, cultural identity, narrative space

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется лингвокультурологическое значение топонимов в английском фольклоре на материале эпоса *Beowulf* и английских народных сказаний: *Robin Hood*, *Jack the Giant Killer* и *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh*. Топонимы в этих произведениях являются не просто географическими обозначениями, но и несут глубокие культурные, символические и исторические значения. Посредством сравнительного анализа исследование показывает, как названия мест отражают культурную идентичность, социальные ценности, мифологическое мировоззрение и оппозицию «свой — чужой». Исследование подчеркивает роль топонимов в формировании художественного пространства и сохранении коллективной памяти в английской устной традиции.

Ключевые слова: топоним, лингвокультурология, фольклор, *Beowulf*, английские народные сказки, культурная идентичность, художественное пространство.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz folkloridagi toponimlarning lingvomadaniy ahamiyati *Beowulf* dostoni hamda ingliz xalq ertaklari — *Robin Hood*, *Jack the Giant Killer* va *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh* misolida tadqiq etiladi. Ushbu asarlardagi toponimlar nafaqat geografik nomlar, balki chuqur madaniy, ramziy va tarixiy ma’nolarni ham ifodalaydi. Qiyosiy tahlil orqali tadqiqot joy nomlari madaniy identitet, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar, mifologik dunyoqarash hamda “o’zga — begona” oppozitsiyasini qanday aks ettirishini ko’rsatadi. Tadqiqot ingliz og’zaki ijodi an’analarda toponimlarning badiiy makonni shakllantirish va jamoaviy xotirani saqlashdagi rolini yoritadi.

Kalit so’zlar: toponim, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, folklor, *Beowulf*, ingliz xalq ertaklari, madaniy identitet, badiiy makon.

Toponyms have been widely studied in linguistics and literary onomastics as important carriers of historical and cultural meaning. According to Hough, “place names preserve evidence of cultural identity and historical memory” (Hough, 2016, p. 4). In linguoculturology, toponyms are viewed not only as geographical markers but also as linguistic units reflecting a nation’s worldview and traditions.

Scholars of Anglo-Saxon literature have analyzed the role of place names in *Beowulf*. Tolkien states that the poem combines “myth, history, and heroic tradition” (Tolkien, 1936, p. 15), while Anderson notes that toponyms such as Heorot, Geatland, and Denmark help construct tribal and

political identity (Anderson, 1999, p. 72). These place names also symbolize the opposition between safe civilized space and dangerous unknown territory.

English folk tales have likewise attracted scholarly attention for their cultural symbolism. Researchers emphasize that locations such as Sherwood Forest in *Robin Hood* represent freedom and resistance against authority (Briggs, 1970, p. 211). In tales like *Jack the Giant Killer* and *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh*, toponyms create a mythical atmosphere while preserving elements of regional folklore and collective memory.

Although folklore and literary onomastics have been studied separately, comparative linguocultural analysis of toponyms in *Beowulf* and English folk tales remains limited. Therefore, this research examines how place names function as cultural and symbolic elements in English oral tradition.

This research applies a qualitative linguocultural approach to the study of toponyms in English folklore literature. The main sources of the research are the Anglo-Saxon epic *Beowulf* and the English folk tales *Robin Hood*, *Jack the Giant Killer*, and *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh*.

The study uses descriptive, comparative, and contextual analysis methods. First, toponyms found in the selected texts were identified and classified according to their historical, geographical, and symbolic characteristics. Then, their linguistic and cultural meanings were analyzed within the context of the narratives. Special attention was paid to the functions of place names in representing cultural identity, mythological worldview, and the opposition between familiar and unfamiliar spaces.

The comparative method was used to determine similarities and differences in the use of toponyms in epic literature and folk tales. In addition, elements of literary onomastics and linguoculturology were employed to interpret how geographical names reflect the cultural values and collective memory of the English people.

The theoretical basis of the research relies on works related to linguoculturology, folklore studies, and literary onomastics, particularly the studies of Hough (2016), Tolkien (1936), and Briggs (1970).

Toponyms in English folklore literature perform not only geographical but also cultural and symbolic functions. In the analyzed texts, place names help create narrative space, reflect social values, and preserve historical memory. The study shows that toponyms in *Beowulf* are more historically grounded, while in folk tales they are often symbolic and mythological.

In *Beowulf*, toponyms such as **Heorot**, **Geatland**, and **Denmark** represent political power, tribal identity, and social order. Heorot, the great mead hall, symbolizes civilization, unity, and royal authority. In contrast, the swamp and Grendel's dwelling represent chaos and danger. Tolkien notes that the epic combines historical reality with mythical imagination (Tolkien, 1936, p. 18). Therefore, place names in *Beowulf* help construct the opposition between "safe" and "hostile" spaces.

In *Robin Hood*, the toponym **Sherwood Forest** has strong cultural symbolism. The forest functions as a place of freedom, justice, and resistance against oppression, whereas **Nottingham** symbolizes official authority and social inequality. According to Briggs, forests in English folklore often represent spaces outside social control (Briggs, 1970, p. 214).

In *Jack the Giant Killer*, many locations are imaginary or generalized. These toponyms mainly create a magical atmosphere and emphasize the hero's journey through dangerous and unknown territories. Unlike *Beowulf*, geographical accuracy is less important than symbolic meaning.

Similarly, in *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh*, the real regional place name **Spindleston Heugh** connects the narrative with local Northumbrian folklore. The toponym strengthens the authenticity of the legend while transforming the location into a mythological space associated with supernatural events.

Table 1.

Linguocultural functions of toponyms in the selected works

Literary Work	Main Toponyms	Function of Toponyms	Cultural Meaning
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<i>Beowulf</i>	Heorot, Geatland, Denmark	Historical and political identification	Power, tribal identity, civilization
<i>Robin Hood</i>	Sherwood Forest, Nottingham	Social and symbolic contrast	Freedom vs. authority
<i>Jack the Giant Killer</i>	Giant lands, castles	Mythological setting	Danger, adventure, heroism
<i>The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh</i>	Spindleston Heugh	Regional and legendary localization	Collective memory, folklore tradition

The analysis demonstrates that toponyms in English folklore literature reflect the worldview and cultural values of English society. They function as important linguocultural markers that connect narrative space with historical memory, mythology, and national identity.

The present research examined the linguocultural functions of toponyms in the Anglo-Saxon epic *Beowulf* and the English folk tales *Robin Hood*, *Jack the Giant Killer*, and *The Laidly Worm of Spindleston Heugh*. The analysis demonstrated that place names in these works serve not only as geographical references but also as important cultural and symbolic elements.

The study revealed that toponyms in *Beowulf* mainly reflect historical reality, tribal identity, and political structure, while in English folk tales they often create symbolic and mythological spaces connected with freedom, danger, heroism, and collective memory. Toponyms such as Heorot, Sherwood Forest, and Spindleston Heugh contribute to the construction of narrative space and express the worldview of English culture.

Furthermore, the comparative analysis showed that epic literature and folk tales use toponyms differently according to their genre characteristics. However, in both traditions, place names preserve cultural heritage and reflect the relationship between language, history, and folklore. Therefore, toponyms can be considered important linguocultural markers in English oral and literary tradition.

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